

Chemical Studies on *Lanka* Tobacco (Indigenous to India) and its Smoke. 3. Lipid Constituents

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Lanka tobacco and its smoke are shown to contain C25-C36 n-alkanes, C27-C35 isoalkanes and C28-C34 anteisoalkanes. Other major components are solanesol, higher fatty acids, α -4,8,13-duvatriene-1,3-diol, neophytadiene and fatty alcohols. The minor terpenes found are phytol, squalene, cycloartenol, 24-methylene cycloartanol and β -amyrin. The leaf and smoke contain the major sterols (cholesterol, campesterol, stigmasterol and β -sitosterol) along with fucosterol which is reported in tobacco for the first time. The transfer rates of these lipid components from leaf to smoke are also reported.

LANKA tobacco is an unique type of indigenous air-cured tobacco grown to a limited extent in the deltaic islands (called *lankas*) of the Godavari and Krishna rivers of Andhra Pradesh in India. In addition to the normal way of smoking a certain section of rural populace smoke the *Chuttas* (cheroots) made out of *lanka* tobacco in the reverse fashion keeping the burning zone in the closed mouth, running a high risk of palate cancer¹. Tobacco lipids are related to the leaf quality and aroma² and are important precursors in the generation of the smoke carcinogens like smoke PAH³. The transfer rates of various lipids from leaf to smoke were reported⁴. The present study was undertaken to determine the transfer rates from leaf to smoke.

Experimental

Top grade leaves of cured and fermented (pit-cured) *lanka* tobacco (composite of *Kotaku* and *baru* grades) were collected from the bulk crop (cv: DR-1) grown in Venkatanagaram *lankas* of CTRI farm. The cultural operations, harvesting and curing methods were as described by Murty *et al.*⁴. The lamina portion of the leaf was dried at 60° and powdered. Cigarettes were made from shreds on a Hauni-Baby machine (Heinr-Borgwaldt, Hamburg) and smoked on a CSM 101 machine to collect total particulate matter (TPM) by Coresta method⁴. The TPM yield was 45.36 mg per g dry tobacco smoked.

Lanka tobacco powder was extracted with petroleum ether and weight of the extract was 5.12% of tobacco. The extract was partitioned with 90%

methanol, concentrated and suspended in ether. Bases, acids and neutrals were separated by treating with 6 N H₂SO₄, 5% NaHCO₃, 5% KOH solutions. The total neutrals (designated as S₁) was chromatographed on neutral alumina eluted with petroleum ether-benzene (1:1), benzene-ether (1:1) and methanol. The eluates were monitored by tlc. PEN after concentration was treated with acetone and stored in deep freeze when a white precipitate (S₂) was obtained and the filtrate was designated as S₄. Petroleum ether-benzene eluate was designated as S₅ and the other eluates as S₆, S₇ and S₈. The residual filtrate of S₈ was designated as S₁₀. The methanol eluate was hydrolysed with 5% KOH to get neutrals S₉ and acids S₁₀.

Sterols were separated from *lanka* tobacco by Keller's modified procedure⁵ of Stedman's original digitonide precipitation method. The total sterol fraction amounting to 0.31% of tobacco was designated as S₁₄.

The leaf and smoke lipids (S₁ and S₁₄) were hydrolysed and fractionated⁷ on silicic acid column. Gc analysis was carried out with a Hewlett-Packard 5840 instrument equipped with a stainless column (0.46 m x 2 mm) containing 5% Dexil 300 on 100/120 mesh Chromosorb W-AW (temp., 100-325° at 6° min⁻¹, injector temp. 275°, FID, hydrogen flow rate 38 ml min⁻¹). Peaks were measured on an autolab system IV electronic integrator. Identification of the components was based on comparison with authentic samples. Fucosterol was assumed to respond like sitosterol and triterpenoids like β -amyrin, phytol and α -tocopherol were estimated as per the detector response of the internal stan-

TABLE 1—HYDROCARBON LEVELS AND ISOMER DISTRIBUTION IN Lanka TOBACCO LEAF AND TPM

	C25	C26	C27	C28	C29	C30	C31	C32	C33	C34	C35	C36
PEN												
Tobacco ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) ^a	11.4	9.6	79.0	18.0	178.0	139.0	678.0	181.0	245.0	11.4	6.5	1.5
% distribution	0.7	0.6	5.1	1.2	11.7	8.9	49.5	11.6	15.7	0.7	0.4	0.1
iso	—	—	1.0	9.0	25.0	10.0	37.0	10.0	35.0	12.0	30.0	—
anteiso	—	—	—	9.0	1.0	55.0	2.0	55.0	3.0	79.0	—	—
normal	100.0	100.0	99.0	81.0	74.0	35.0	61.0	35.0	63.0	39.0	70.0	100.0
TPM												
Tobacco ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) ^a	7.2 ^b	6.4 ^b	22.8	7.7	95.9	37.3	125.0	34.3	32.1	2.3	1.0	0.1
% distribution	2.3	2.0	9.1	2.4	11.2	11.7	39.2	10.7	9.8	0.7	0.3	0.03
iso	—	—	1.0	8.0	34.0	13.0	32.0	9.0	38.0	5.0	20.0	—
anteiso	—	—	—	9.0	2.0	70.0	4.0	71.0	6.0	61.0	—	—
normal	100.0	100.0	99.0	83.0	65.0	27.0	64.0	19.0	56.0	33.0	80.0	100.0
% Transfer (from leaf to smoke)												
	63	67	36	43	20	27	18	19	18	20	16	7

^aAnalysed (as in Ref. 3) on a HP 5840 gc modified for capillary column (25 m x 0.25 mm id) SE-54 silica column; temp. 150°–280° at 3° min⁻¹; linear flow velocity 25 cm s⁻¹ of H₂, corrected for differences in detector response; branched isomers assumed to respond like normal isomers.

^bContaminated with alkenes.

TABLE 2—LEVELS OF MAJOR COMPONENTS IN LEAF PEN (S₁) AND TPM (S_{1.6})

Component	Leaf PEN (S ₁)			TPM (S _{1.6})		
	Free* $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ tobacco	Hydrolysed** $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ tobacco	Percent bound	Free* $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ tobacco smoked	Total**	Percent bound
Neophytadiene	—	549.0	—	—	201.0	—
C16 : 0 acid	893.0	1 490.0	40.0	313.0	392.0	20.0
C18 : 1 + C18 : 2 + C18 : 3 acids	1 091.0	2 019.0	46.0	347.0	490.0	29.0
C18 : 0 acid	269.0	466.0	42.0	117.0	126.0	7.0
α -duvatrienediol	—	1 070.0	—	—	108.0	—
Bombiprenone + Solanesene	—	1 740.0	—	—	535.0	—
Solanesol	18 300.0	20 700.0	11.6	1 710.0	1 930.0	14.0

*Whole fraction analysis after treatment with 1 : 1 BSTFA – DMF analysed on Dexil 800 column.

**Analysis of whole fraction after hydrolysis with KOH in 85% aqueous ethanol. All data are corrected for detector response. Bombiprenone and solanesenes are assumed to respond like solanesol.

dards. Branched chain isomers respond like normal isomers.

Each fraction (1–1.5 mg) and 1,3-dimyrustin (50 mg) were placed in a microauto-injector vial, the solvent was removed under nitrogen, silylating mixture (50 ml, 1 : 1 BSTFA and DMF) added and heated for 30 min at 76°. Quantitative data was obtained from the hydrolysed and unhydrolysed lipids of leaf and TPM (S₁, S₁₋₃, S_{1.6} and S_{1.6-3}).

Results and Discussion

The quantitative data on the individual paraffin hydrocarbons (normal, iso and anteiso) ranging from C25 to C36 in leaf and TPM along with percent transfers are presented in Table 1. The composition of C25 to C36 (n-alkanes), C27 to C35 (isoalkanes) and C28 to C34 (anteisoalkanes) is presented in leaf and TPM. This is in agreement with Stedman's^{1,2} observation. The major alkane is hentriacontane both in leaf and TPM. The transfer rates of alkanes from leaf to smoke is approximately in proportion to the leaf composi-

tion³. The percentage composition of alkanes in Lanka tobacco (0.16%) and smoke TPM (0.03%) and the transfer rate (20%) are comparable to that reported³. It is interesting to note that as the molecular weight of alkanes increases the transfer rate decreases, which may be due to less volatility from leaf to smoke. Normal alkanes dominated both in leaf and smoke.

The data on the levels of major components in leaf PEN (S₁) and TPM (S_{1.6}) are presented in Table 2. The major component in leaf and smoke is solanesol which is present in free and esterified form. Only 9.6% is transferred to smoke and the rest may be degraded^{1,2} or may contribute to the formation of PAH^{1,2}. The next major group is higher fatty acids which are present in bound and free forms. The transfer rate of ~25% is slightly higher than the reported value (14%)^{1,2}, for non-filter cigarettes. It is seen that neophytadiene was transferred to smoke by 37%, the rest getting degraded as reported by Chortyk *et al.*³. The other component α -4,8,13-duvatriene-1,3-diol was transferred to smoke to the extent of 10%. If

petroleum ether extract was not pre-extracted with 90% methanol, higher concentration of this compound would have been found in the leaf. The other compounds found in S_1 and S_{16} are bombiprenone and solanesenes, which are transferred to the smoke to the extent of 30%. Contrary to the reported views¹³, bombiprenone and solanesol are natural products of tobacco.

The data presented in Table 3 show that the unsaturated C18 acids and C16:0 acid accounted for about 90% of the leaf acids and about 77% of

TABLE 3—LEVELS OF SELECTED LIPIDS IN LEAF AND SMOKE

Compd.	Tobacco $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$	Tobacco smoked $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$	% Transfer
<i>Acids</i>			
C14:0	107.0	30.3	28.0
C16:0	1 490.0	392.0	26.3
C18:1+C18:2; 2+C18:3	2 020.0	490.0	24.3
C18:0	466.0	126.3	27.3
<i>Fatty alcohols</i>			
C20	17.8	2.68	15.0
C22	85.9	6.98	19.4
C24	5.3	—	—
C26	4.3	—	—
<i>Terpenes</i>			
Neophytadiene	549.0	201.0	37.0
Phytol	341.0	48.5	12.8
Squalene	47.1	11.7	24.8
β -Amyrin	45.9	7.7	16.8
Cycloartenol	24.0	4.8	20.0
24-Methylene cycloartenol	46.9	6.6	14.1
α -Tocopherol	29.1	—	—
Solanesol	20 700.0	1 980.0	9.6

TPM acids. The percent transfer of the acids from leaf to smoke varied from 24.3 to 28.0. Severson *et al.*¹² reported the transfer rates of acids in US non-filter and filter cigarettes as 14 and 8%, respectively. The data on *lanka* tobacco is in fair agreement with the results of Bellin¹⁴ who reported 24–26% for flue-cured tobacco and 12–49% for burley tobacco. Hoffmann and Wozniowski¹⁵ observed that the lower the fatty acid level in tobacco, the higher was the transfer rate to smoke and vice versa. Similar trend was observed in *lanka* tobacco. Fatty alcohols in *lanka* tobacco are represented by even-numbered alcohols, viz. C20, C22, C24 and C26, while in TPM, only the first two alcohols were present. Docosanol, is the major alcohol in TPM with a transfer rate of 19.4%.

The major components of terpene fraction are solanesol and neophytadiene with transfer rates of 9.6 and 37%, respectively, while Severson *et al.*⁸ reported 9.4 and 18.1%, respectively. α -Tocopherol was found in the leaf only. The other minor terpenes are phytol, squalene, cycloartenol, 24-methylene cycloartenol and β -amyrin with their transfer rates ranging from 12.8 to 24.8%. According to Severson *et al.*⁸, the transfer rates of terpenes for US non-filter and filter cigarettes were 10 and

5%, respectively. The presence of the three 4,4'-dimethylsterols in green tobacco was reported by Reid¹⁶. The terpenoid compounds are potent precursors of smoke PAH¹⁷. Phytol and squalene are also potent PAH precursors.

The quantitative data on the leaf and TPM sterols and the corresponding dienes (TPM only) are presented in Table 4. Along with 4-desmethylsterols (cholesterol, campesterol, stigmasterol, sitosterol) *lanka* leaf and TPM contained fucosterol also. This appears to be the first report on fucosterol as tobacco constituent. The sterols are transferred to the extent of 17.3 to 24.9%. This is in fair agreement with figures of 20% reported by Schmeltz *et al.*¹⁸. Mass spectral data of its TMS derivative was found to be identical with that in Registry of Mass Spectral Data.

TABLE 4—LEVELS OF STEROLS AND RELATED DIENES IN LEAF AND SMOKE

Compd.	Level in $\mu\text{g/g}$ tobacco	Level in $\mu\text{g/g}$ tobacco smoked	Percent transfer
Cholesterol	120	27.8	23.2
Cholestadiene	—	1.9	1.6 ^a
Campesterol	208	47.5	23.0
Campestadiene	—	5.6	2.76 ^a
Stigmasterol	317	78.8	24.9
Stigmastadiene	—	5.9	1.9 ^a
β -Sitosterol	200	43.9	22.0
Sitostadiene	—	5.2	2.6 ^a
Fucosterol	90	16.2	17.8
Fucostadiene	—	0.2	0.2 ^a

(Corrected for detector response, dienes assumed to have detector response identical to the nearest eluting hydrocarbon).

^aPercent of leaf sterol pyrolytically degraded and transferred to TPM as diene.

Fraction S_4 represents the remainder after the removal of alkane precipitate from petroleum ether eluate. It is composed of neophytadiene, alkanes and solanesenes, which are the dehydration products of solanesol. This fraction after hydrolysis showed the same composition indicating that they are in free form. The major component of S_4 is solanesenes.

Before saponification, fraction S_5 contained esterified sterols and triterpenols. After saponification, the neutral portion showed the presence of the usual 4-desmethylsterols (cholesterol, campesterol, stigmasterol, β -sitosterol) and fucosterol along with 4,4'-dimethylsterols (cycloartenol and 24-methylenecycloartenol). The acid moieties of S_5 comprised of C14:0 to C18:0 and three unsaturated C18 acids (C18:1, C18:2, C18:3).

The composition of the fraction S_6 showed bombiprenone and a mixture of solanesols as major components. These components are presented in free form originally because after hydrolysis, the same composition was indicated. The composition of S_7 revealed that solanesol is its major component. The minor components of this fraction are the three fatty alcohols (C20, C22 and C24) and the usual

4-desmethylsterols and triterpenols, β -amyrin and cycloartenol.

The fractions S_8 and S_{18} obtained from the other eluate of alumina column, is a mixture of sterols and tocopherols. S_{14} refers to the total free sterols obtained by Stedman's procedure. Qualitatively, these fractions are similar showing the presence of cholesterol, campesterol, stigmasterol, sitosterol and fucosterol. Additionally, the precipitate S_8 contained α -tocopherol. Quantitative data on sterol composition in these fractions as well as S_1 and S_{18} are presented in Table 4. It can be seen that stigmasterol was the major sterol followed by campesterol in all the fractions. Fucosterol is the minor component accounting for less than 10% of the total sterols. The transfer rate of the total sterols from leaf to smoke is 24.7%.

The gc profiles of methanol eluate before and after hydrolysis (S_8 and S_{10}) showed that the non-saponifiables are unidentified high molecular weight polar compounds while the acidic moieties contained the usual fatty acids (C14 : 0 to C18 : 0). Thus, the methanol eluate is composed of fatty acid esters of high molecular weight alcohols.

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